

Basics of Media Competence Development in School Leaders

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Abstract: In the article, the issue of media competence development among school leaders is discussed. According to the author, the use of media tools to learn special methods and use them in active practice gives an opportunity to confront stereotypes of thinking, causes the development of new ideas and views in the participants of the educational process. The development of media competence in the heads of secondary educational institutions helps to form basic universal skills to achieve high efficiency in various areas of managerial activity.

Keywords: school leaders, media competence, management, managerial activity, ability to improvise, universal skills.

Introduction.

The rapid development of the information society, the emergence and wide distribution of network and multimedia technologies made it possible for school managers to implement a new approach to the development of media competence. The need for conscious management of the information and educational environment did not appear today, but due to the rapid development of information flows, information volume and information technologies, its relevance is increasing day by day.

The formation of media literacy skills in school leaders, which allows them to successfully communicate in the modern media space, is an urgent requirement of the modern era. In connection with the above, the perception of media technologies as a powerful tool for developing critical thinking, obtaining information and necessary knowledge, accumulating values, and forming vital competencies is one of the priority and important tasks of a modern leader [1]. Therefore, taking into account the rapid development of everything related to the information space in the modern world, the management activity culture is enriched with the newest function. Therefore, the task of media management, which allows creating the potential of universality that helps school leaders to act in changing conditions, enters the field of pedagogical research.

The acquisition of media technologies by school leaders is becoming an important resource for increasing the effectiveness of management in general.

Research Methodology.

The basics of developing media competence in the heads of this school were written. Forms and methods grouping, comparative analysis, selective observation methods were used to develop media competence of school leaders. Logical and structural analysis, grouping and comparison methods were used as research methodology.

Literature review.

N.R. Rustamova gives a unique interpretation of the concept of "media competence" in her research. For him, it is "the result of the personal-subjective acquisitions of the head of the school in the process of formal and informal education, and describes the individual readiness of a person to manage mass media" [3, p. 58], he writes.

V.N. Vvedensky stated that "personal information culture is one of the components of the general culture of a person, a set of information worldview and knowledge system, purposeful independent activity to optimally satisfy individual information needs using both traditional and new information technologies providing skills. This component is the most important factor of successful professional and non-professional activities, as well as social security of the individual in the information society" [2, p. 21].

A.V. Fedorov pedagogical support is "a special direction of pedagogical activity that consistently implements the principles of person-oriented education, which not only declares the student as an educational subject, but also helps to solve problems between adults and children, overcome difficulties, individual Subject-subject aimed at self-development, strives to ensure equal relations" [4, p. 69], believes.

U. Nurgatina stated that "psychological-pedagogical support of the manager is an integral, systematically organized pedagogical process of a system of measures aimed at forming the pedagogical team's readiness for professional activity, developing personal qualities and social-professional competences" [5, p. 69].

Researchers around the world emphasize the need for media education for school managers. School managers with media competence are expected to be able to:

encourage and develop a desire to ask conscious problematic questions about media;

independently search for media information to answer various questions,

to help school managers develop the ability to use a variety of primary information sources to examine issues and then draw generalized conclusions;

organize discussions about the pedagogical team, which learns to listen with tolerance and courtesy, their opinions, including media texts;

encourage them to reflect on their media experiences and act on the insights they gain [3; 5; 6].

Analysis and results.

The basis for increasing the role of the cultural factor in solving modern management problems is related to several circumstances: "first of all, social regulators of social life and others (economic, legal, political) are becoming more and more important in connection with the requirements of the information revolution. Second. , they become more and more systematic in the sum of all interacting forces in society, penetrating the activities of every element of society and thus expanding their sphere of influence.

Media culture includes "the culture of information production and transmission, as well as the culture of its perception; it can also be an indicator of the level of development of a person who is able to perceive, analyze, evaluate media text, engage in media creativity, acquire new knowledge through media, and others[7, 87 -b].

Media management regulates this process, helps to modernize the socio-cultural sphere and form a new type of personality. It follows that "media management" is a polysemantic term that:

a social and economic institution that affects a person's lifestyle, the sphere of politics and culture, and entrepreneurship;

a set of persons engaged in management work in the field of non-material, but spiritual production and distribution of media products (newspapers, magazines, books, films, TV and radio programs, Internet sites, multimedia, etc.);

a scientific science that studies the technical, organizational and socio-economic aspects of managing the media industry, the processes of information production and consumption, the impact of information and communication technologies on society, etc. [8, p. 112].

"Media management" is an integrated management system for the production, distribution and consumption of the information and communication field, including media policy, e-commerce, innovative technologies and other means [9, p. 56].

The media space of a modern school is an open social system of information media. The communication technologies used in the media space of the modern school are often represented by web pages (sites) on the Internet, blogs on social networks, printed publications, studio editions of television news and programs. The audience of the school media space is teachers, administrators, parents, representatives of educational institutions of various levels, specialists in the field of educational management and other social partners, which are not only internal to the media space of a modern school.

The media space of a modern school solves several problems at the same time. First, it forms a qualified and demanding audience. Secondly, the school ensures the principle of openness of the educational space and provides an opportunity to interact with external mass media. Thirdly, it develops professional skills and competencies of schoolchildren involved in this type of activity.

School media is a reliable basis for forming and testing the competences of the pedagogical team. An interest in socio-political media acquired in school can have an important professional direction. These types of activities help to form a system of information perception and analysis both in the classroom and outside of the classroom, the implementation of project activities not only provides school leaders with various information skills (selecting, collecting, processing information, using it in other presentation in the form), but also faces the need to acquire technological skills (video editing, computer layout creation).

The head of the school should teach the pedagogical team to act in mass media, monitor their influence and analyze the consequences of such influence. In addition, it is important to learn how to evaluate the reliability of the obtained data.

According to B.A. Iskakov, the head of the school should acquire the basics of media culture by himself, and become influential mediators in the communication between the media environment of the institution and the pedagogical team [10]. This leads to the need to pay special attention to how to organize the media space in a modern school.

One of the main values of the described model for creating a school media space is the ability to develop creative and critical thinking, mastering experience and tools for media literacy, independent search, and the ability to correctly use information flows. effective communication, solving educational, cognitive and other personal problems and tasks, that is, aimed not at knowledge, but at gaining managerial experience of the manager.

School leaders are required not only to be able to shape media tools in the existing technological platform according to their mission and concept, but also to teach school teachers the basics of media literacy, which allows them to create conditions for the formation and implementation of their position.

School leaders should be involved in working with the media space of a modern school - after all, they intuitively, quickly and correctly understand all the latest trends in the world of communication and understand that information and communication competence is an integral part of modern education. In our society, learning the latest technology is the shortest path to success and self-realization.

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